

The Theory of Empowerment Reciprocity: My Personal Nursing Philosophy for Advanced Practice

Clelie Crochet Hebert

College of Nursing, University of Colorado

NURS 6009: Theory Foundation for Advanced Nursing

Dr. Mary Mackenburg-Mohn

December 5, 2022

Part I

Human interaction is at the center of nursing. These interactions drive results and outcomes. My philosophy focuses on how to optimize human interaction to achieve desired outcomes. Throughout this course, I have read different theorists' work which explains phenomena about human behavior and interaction. Of particular interest to me was Carper's ways of knowing, Roy's adaptation model, and Resnick's theory of self-efficacy. When considering human interaction, each theorist provides elements I believe are parts of a whole to achieve effective interaction which is central to nursing. By knowing self, people can adequately adapt in an ever-changing environment, enabling perceived and actual self-efficacy to achieve desired outcomes through human interaction. When self-aware and effectively navigating adaptation, humans will reciprocally empower one another to achieve more and become more through their interactions.

Carper's exploration of Ways of Knowing, particularly personal knowing, resonated with me. How we view and see ourselves is paramount to acknowledge because it impacts our ability to relate to others. Nursing is not just fixing disease or problems, it's about having relationships with patients that build trust, enable influence, and instill confidence. Personal knowledge is challenging in both nursing and everyday life (Carper, 1978). The inability to know self and be able to sustain genuine connections is why there is discord in so many relationships and why people don't succeed in their endeavors. When we truly master ourselves, fully understanding who and what we are, we can adjust as needed to create harmony and unity in the world. This requires a great deal of humility. It is uncomfortable to recognize shortcomings, ineffective tendencies, laziness, and inadequacy. However, it is only when we take a naked look at our inner self, that we can make choices to be better and be in relationships more authentically. This requires that we also acknowledge that humans are complex, ever changing, with

free will to express their innermost thoughts and ideas in their own way. We must find the ability to partner with a diverse expression of self in our patients, coworkers, friends and family.

Once we know ourselves, we can then modify our actions to meet the needs of the interaction. These interactions lead to the goal of creating a better world and becoming better ourselves. However, the ability to do that is very much dependent on our actual and perceived self-efficacy. Resnick's theory of self-efficacy was essential in the development of my philosophy. This theory describes two different elements central to self-efficacy. Self-efficacy expectation are personal conclusions about one's capacity to perform something. Outcome expectations are judgements about what will occur if performing something will be successful (Smith & Liehr, 2018). The perception of self-efficacy is dependent on knowing self fully.

Finally, Roy's adaptive modes of self-concept and group identity are parallel to knowing self. Self-concept is what one believes an feels or holds true about himself. These thoughts come from internal perception and perceptions others have (Smith, 2020) This ultimately guides behavior. Roy's interdependence mode explains that our lives are interconnected with others. Success in this interconnectedness brings about positive adaptation for individuals and groups.

Table 1: Ladder of Abstraction

This top tier of the ladder focuses on what is true about reality and includes several assumptions. The interactive-integrative paradigm views people as reciprocal interacting entities and holds that change is probabilistic and related to many factors (Smith & Liehr, 2018). My first assumption is humans decide how to behave and exercise influence over their actions. If this were untrue, we would be at the complete mercy of the external world. We aren't helpless though; we are autonomous and capable of executing our own will. Additionally, humans are responsible for entering the process of deriving, sustaining, and transforming their communities, organizations, families and their lives. This comes from Roy's Adaptation Model. Each of us can influence change in our worlds. I also conclude that the purpose of life is becoming the best version of yourself, making our worlds the best versions they can be, and enabling the same for others. Finally, positive interactions are dependent on understanding and mutual respect and value. When people feel seen, heard, valued, they will give more of their genuine self to an interaction. This allows for a synergistic encounter to occur.

The theoretical rung helps define things conceptually. My concepts include knowing self, humility, self-efficacy and empowerment reciprocity. Knowing self is more than just knowing yourself. It is the ability to know another and understand their world and experiences as if you were yourself in it (White, 1995). By acknowledging and understanding our values, tendencies, prejudices, and nuances of our life's journey, we are consequently closer to understanding how that shows up during interactions with others. Without acknowledging these attributes of ourselves, it is probable that we exhibit judgement, lack of empathy, and disregard toward others. Interacting with someone who does not care leads to mistrust. It is unlikely that the interaction will lead to desired outcomes.

That level of knowing self is impossible without humility. Humility is the ability to acknowledge parts of ourselves that bar us from reaching connectedness to others, becoming the best version of ourselves and creating a better world. We must adapt, change and grow to fulfill our potential and help others achieve theirs. Without humility, we lack the ability to change because pride and ego dominate our perceptions. Achieving humility comes from internal thoughts and reflection, but also from accepting feedback from the outside world. The results of our choices provide us with insight about how efficacious we are in our human interactions. Adaptation occurs after considering those discoveries.

By knowing self and utilizing humility to identify areas needing modification, we can develop a sense of ability to accomplish tasks and succeed in our endeavors. Self-efficacy is affirming thought about our capacity to accomplish something that will help us achieve our goals. What good is it to know an action is needed if we don't believe we can do it? Or what if we believe we can accomplish something but don't believe it will matter? Knowing we can do a thing and knowing it will mean matter lead to meaningful self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is knowing that we have the power to have positive human interactions which will ultimately lead to successful completion of goals.

With awareness of ourselves and of others, using humility to change ourselves to meet the needs of the situation, and knowing that we can achieve our goals, we reach the pinnacle of human interaction. Empowerment reciprocity is mutually enabling those we interact with to become more and achieve more. When you show up authentically without pride and ego, you leave room for the person you are interacting with to do the same. This creates an atmosphere of respect and trust. You encourage each other to achieve self-efficacy and empower each other to achieve goals. So how do we do that practically in a healthcare setting? How does a nurse do that with the patient? How does a team or organization realize this level of functioning? That will be the focus of my advanced practice and explored in the final rung of the ladder of abstraction.

Part II

My role as an advanced practice nurse will not be a typical one. I will be a CNS in the Army. The Army utilizes AGCNS in an organizational leadership role. My focus will be to make emergency trauma nursing more effective. This only happens when members of the team interact in ways to facilitate one another's ability to become the best version of themselves. I have witnessed ineffective teams as well as highly functioning and successful teams. The teams that achieve greatness are focused on clear, effective and respectful interactions. The youngest, least experienced member of the team has the same sense of value and ability to influence change as the highest-ranking trauma surgeon.

Although I am just beginning this journey in advanced practice nursing, I will apply my philosophy in several ways. The proposals and tasks I will describe below will be the empirical rung of my ladder of abstraction. I will create an organizational program that will foster mutual respect and understanding between team members. This program will focus on achieving the elements of my philosophy: knowing self, humility, self-efficacy and empowerment reciprocity. This may end up looking like a "human interaction bootcamp" or a pre-deployment relationship building exercise. The creation and refining of a program like this will take a lot of time to accomplish.

On a smaller scale, I can implement a practice change program focused on bringing in current evidence into emergency medicine. The ability to implement evidence-based practice requires each element of my philosophy. The team implementing change must "know self" in terms of how and why their current practice is what it is. Then you must create a shared understanding of why practice must change (organizational humility). The team must feel as though they will be successful in creating change and believe that their change will matter (self-efficacy). And finally, the team must support and empower each other to continue sustaining the change. Additionally, I can apply these principles to my individual interaction with others. I will strive to create an atmosphere of mutual respect and value. I

will self-reflect and evaluate how my own tendencies and values effect the way I show up in my relationships with others. I will seek to empower myself and others to achieve more and become more.

Implementing my philosophy in practice would also take considerable time and effort. It would be valuable to create and test a tool that measures the effectiveness of leadership's influence over staff. Another tool would be used to measure the degree of mutual respect between team members. It would also be beneficial to conduct qualitative research on team member's perceived ability to influence change in their organization. I believe all of these would help nursing understand why things happen the way they do and provide opportunity for practice change.

After evaluating my theory, I found that there are some positives along with some negatives. When considering its substantive foundation, this theory is focused on nursing and its assumptions are specified. I interpret and explain the phenomenon named and it is rooted in my practice and research experiences. I believe that it has good structural integrity. I clearly defined the concepts and represented their relationships in my ladder of abstraction model. I believe there were not too many concepts. The functional adequacy is where I believe the drawbacks are. Although I believe the theory can be applied to a variety of practice environments and client groups, there are no published examples of its use or examples of its research yet. Although I have identified some empirical tools for future use, they are theoretical themselves and have not yet been created.

My personal philosophy of empowerment reciprocity is a way to look at one of the most central elements of nursing: human interaction. When we have a solid understanding of ourselves and others, we can have authentic and successful relationships that lead to positive interactions. By identifying shortcomings through humility and self-reflection, we can adapt and fit the needs of current situation. When self-aware and effectively navigating adaptation, humans will reciprocally empower one another to achieve more and become more through their interactions.

References

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